

Smarandache's SYNONYMITY TEST

The Smarandache's Synonymity Test:
similar to, and an extension of, the antonym test in psychology,
is a verbal test where the subject must supply as many as possible synonyms
of a given word within a as short as possible period of time.

How to measure it?

The spectrum of supplied synonyms (s), within the measured period of time (t),
shows the subject's level of linguistic neutrosophy: s/t .

George Hammond mentioned that "this test is more related to Intelligence than to Personality" and "besides having a high loading on IQ (or psychometric-g) it might also have a number of specific factors, such as Reading Level, in a factor analysis procedure". "(...) if you gave such a test to a group of subjects, and also included tests for Intelligence, Personality, Reading Ability, etc. and then factored the resulting correlation matrix, I think you would find the highest loading on Reading Level, then IQ, then Personality".

Reference:

Smarandache, Florentin, "Neutrosophy. / Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic", American Research Press, Rehoboth, 1989.